

Effectiveness of a pharmacist-led medication management review service in improving adherence among adult females with depression and anxiety: A two-arm parallel randomized controlled trial

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Abstract

Objective: The study was designed to evaluate the effect of medication management review service (MMR) provided by pharmacist on the medication adherence for females diagnosed with depression and anxiety in Jordan, and to estimate the effect of different patient factors on their medication adherence.

Method: Recruited patients who visited an outpatient psychiatric clinic at the University of Jordan hospital were recruited into this single-blind parallel randomized controlled trial and randomized into active and control groups. Both groups underwent an interview with the pharmacist and answered a questionnaire about medication adherence. Active group patients received the MMR service: pharmacist-delivered counselling on medication adherence, and a letter with recommended changes in the patient's treatment plan was sent to the patient's psychiatrist for implementation. Control group participants did not receive the intervention. Follow-up assessments were completed for all patients at 3 months from baseline.

Results: A total of 73 patients participated in the study (all females according to protocol, mean age = 41.81 ± 0.98). Adherence score for patients indicated that 28.76% of patients had high adherence and 20.54% had medium adherence at baseline. After three months, 43.83% of patients in the intervention group were found to have high adherence compared to 26.02% in the control group ($p = 0.002$). A significant association was found between total adherence score with the number of treatment related problems (TRPs) at follow up for all patients ($R^2 = 0.18$, $P = 0.045$), and for those in the intervention group ($P = 0.017$). There was no significant association between adherence score and other patient factors including age, number of disease per patient, and number of drugs per patient.

Conclusion: Medication Management review service led to a significant improvement in medication adherence score in patients who received the service compared to those who did not. A significant association was found between adherence score and number of TRPs. No other patient factors showed significant association with adherence scores.

Keywords

Pharmaceutical care, Medication Management Review Service, Adherence, Adult Females, Depression, Anxiety, Randomized Controlled Trial

Introduction

Medication adherence, as defined by the World Health Organization (WHO), is “the extent of agreement of a person’s behavior with healthcare provider recommendations” (Burkhart and Sabaté 2003). Encompasses the initiation, implementation, and discontinuation of prescribed regimens (Vrijens et al. 2012). Despite the efficacy demonstrated in clinical trials, treatments often prove less effective in real-world practice, largely due to medication non-adherence (Burkhart and Sabaté 2003). Approximately 50% of patients with chronic diseases in developed countries fail to adhere to their prescribed therapies (Burkhart and Sabaté 2003; Carter et al. 2005), most commonly by discontinuing treatment prematurely or never initiating it at all. This challenge is particularly relevant in Jordan, where mental health services are still developing and pharmacists are underutilized in psychiatric care.

WHO categorizes the determinants of non-adherence into patient-related, disease-related, healthcare system, and socioeconomic factors (Burkhart and Sabaté 2003). Recognizing these influences is essential for designing effective interventions. For instance, excluding patients from treatment decision-making (Haynes et al. 2002), limited health literacy (Raynor 2008), and financial constraints all contribute significantly to poor adherence. The consequences are substantial: non-adherence accounts for 33–69% of medication-related hospitalizations (Kravitz and Melnikow 2004) and imposes a considerable economic burden on healthcare systems, estimated at US\$100–290 billion in the United States, A\$7 billion in Australia, and €1.25 billion in Europe (Osterberg and Blaschke 2005; Cutler et al. 2018). Improving adherence is therefore critical to enhancing healthcare outcomes and system efficiency (Saha et al. 2021).

In mental health care, adherence is particularly vital. Effective treatment strategies for depression and anxiety rely heavily on consistent medication use. Poor adherence to antidepressants increases the risk of relapse, worsens disease severity, heightens suicidal ideation, and escalates healthcare costs (Lindström and Bingefors 2000; Haynes et al. 2002; Burton et al. 2007). Patients’ beliefs about psychiatric medications, misconceptions about side effects, and lack of understanding regarding treatment benefits strongly influence adherence (Fawzi et al. 2012). While physicians are expected to provide adequate information about treatment duration and expected outcomes (Bull et al. 2002), time constraints often hinder thorough patient education (Lin et al. 1995; Bull et al. 2002; Ho et al. 2016). Financial barriers further exacerbate the problem, especially for patients with low income or limited insurance coverage (Lin

et al. 1995; Ho et al. 2016). Although guidelines recommend continuing antidepressants for at least 4–9 months post-remission (Depression Guideline Panel 1993; American Psychiatric Association 2010), studies reveal a gap between physician recommendations and patient awareness, with only 34% of patients informed to continue treatment for six months despite 72% of physicians reporting they provide such guidance (Bull et al. 2002).

Previous studies have highlighted the problem of non-adherence in psychiatric populations (Kondova et al. 2018). The problem was common in Jordan as well. A cross-sectional study found high rates of non-adherence among psychiatric patients, emphasizing the need for targeted interventions (Mukattash et al. 2016). Other research in Jordan has examined adherence in chronic disease populations, showing that higher disease burden, polypharmacy, misperception regarding their disease, and cognitive and economic issues are associated with lower adherence (Basheti et al. 2016a, 2016b; Al-Bahnasi and Basheti 2025).

More recently, mixed-methods evidence from Jordanian healthcare professionals has identified cultural and systemic barriers to adherence, including stigma and limited patient education (Abed et al. 2026). These findings underscore the importance of exploring innovative, culturally sensitive strategies to improve adherence in psychiatric care.

Internationally, pharmacist-led interventions have consistently demonstrated effectiveness in improving adherence among patients with depression and anxiety (Shoji et al. 2023). A scoping review of pharmacist interventions in mental health disorders concluded that structured counseling, monitoring, and follow-up significantly improved adherence outcomes (Haynes et al. 2002). In Japan, a community pharmacy-based study using cognitive behavioral therapy-informed interventions showed improvements in adherence and patient-reported outcomes (Shoji et al. 2023). Similarly, European and U.S. studies have reported that pharmacist coaching and collaborative practice models increased continuation rates of antidepressant therapy (Brook et al. 2005; Rickles et al. 2006). These findings highlight the pharmacist’s unique position as an accessible healthcare provider capable of addressing both clinical and psychosocial barriers to adherence.

Despite this growing body of evidence, no studies in Jordan have specifically evaluated the impact of pharmacist-led Medication Management Review (MMR) on adherence among patients with psychiatric disorders. Given the cultural context, the burden of mental illness, and the accessibility of pharmacists, this study aims to fill that gap by assessing the effect of MMR on adherence among female patients with depression and anxiety.

Pharmacists, due to their accessibility and frequent patient interactions, play a pivotal role in addressing adherence barriers (Finley et al. 2003; Rickles et al. 2006; Basheti et al. 2024). In Jordan, pharmacists are often the primary source of medication advice (Basheti et al. 2014), and services such as Medication Management Review (MMR) have shown promise in optimizing therapeutic outcomes for patients with chronic conditions (Qudah et al. 2018). MMR involves identifying, preventing, and resolving treatment-related problems (TRPs), including adherence issues, through patient-centered counseling and education (Basheti et al. 2016a, 2016b). Given the cultural context, the burden of mental illness, and the accessibility of pharmacists, no previous study has evaluated the effect of MMR on adherence among patients with depression and anxiety.

Females are disproportionately affected by depression and anxiety due to biological, psychological, and socio-cultural factors, including hormonal fluctuations, stress internalization, caregiving responsibilities, and economic inequalities (UWH Review n.d.; Psychology Today n.d.). These challenges are further compounded in Jordan, where cultural barriers often hinder communication between female patients and male healthcare providers, limiting treatment engagement and adherence (Abed et al. 2026). Given these constraints, female clinical pharmacists may be uniquely positioned to overcome cultural barriers, foster trust, and provide patient-centered counseling. However, no previous study has examined the impact of MMR service delivered by female pharmacists to women with depression and/or anxiety. This study therefore seeks to fill this gap by assessing the effectiveness of female pharmacist-led MMR in improving adherence and exploring how patient-specific factors influence treatment outcomes.

This study aims to assess the effectiveness of pharmacist-led MMR services in improving medication adherence among female patients diagnosed with depression and/or anxiety. Additionally, it seeks to explore associations between patient-specific factors—such as age, comorbidities, medication burden, and TRPs—and adherence outcomes.

Methodology

Study design and clinical setting

Study design and participants

This single-blinded randomized controlled trial was conducted at Jordan University Hospital (JUH) in Amman, Jordan, between August 2016 and January 2017. Female patients attending the outpatient psychiatric clinic were recruited. Only the physicians and the female pharmacist who approached the patients were aware of group assignments, ensuring blinding of participants. Ethical approval was obtained from the Jordan University ethics committee.

Inclusion criteria required participants to be Jordanian females, Arabic speakers, aged 18 years or older, residing in Jordan for at least 12 months and planning to remain

for the follow-up period, with a physician diagnosis of depression and/or anxiety. Eligible patients had not been hospitalized prior to the study and had been on stable medication regimens for at least four weeks before enrollment. Exclusion criteria included acute illnesses requiring monitoring, cognitive or sensory impairments that could hinder communication with the pharmacist, and plans to travel before the end of the follow-up period.

Patients were randomized into intervention and control groups using a predetermined computer-generated randomization list (www.randomization.com).

Medication Management Review (MMR) process

Following recruitment, patients were approached by a female clinical pharmacist at the outpatient psychiatric clinic. The pharmacist interviewed both intervention and control groups, collecting demographic data, identifying TRPs, and assessing adherence using a validated medication adherence questionnaire (Morisky et al. 1986; Basheti et al. 2016a, 2016b).

Patients in the intervention group received individualized counseling sessions (15–20 minutes) focused on the importance of timely medication use, continuation of antidepressant and/or anxiolytic therapy, and strategies to overcome adherence barriers. Each patient's specific adherence challenges were discussed, and education was provided regarding their medical condition and prescribed treatments. When TRPs requiring physician input were identified (e.g., dose adjustments or therapy changes), the pharmacist prepared written recommendations for the physician. Physicians either accepted or rejected these recommendations, providing justification when necessary, and patients were asked to confirm any changes during the study (those patients were contacted by the clinical pharmacist and asked to visit the physician). Counseling addressed misconceptions about medications, clarified the nature of the patient's condition, and explained expected adverse effects, with the aim of improving adherence and treatment continuity. The control group received assessment only, without counseling or intervention.

After three months, all patients in both groups were re-interviewed by the pharmacist to reassess adherence, TRPs, and depression/anxiety scales.

For ethical reasons, the control group received the counseling delivered to the intervention group after the study ended.

Adherence assessment

Patients' adherence was evaluated through structured interviews using the validated and published adherence questionnaire designed based on the 8-item Morisky Medication Adherence Scale (MMAS-8) questionnaire (Morisky et al. 1986; Basheti et al. 2016a, 2016b). The pharmacist administered the questionnaire to both intervention and control groups, assessing adherence behaviors and identifying reasons for non-adherence.

The adherence questionnaire includes eight questions addressing patient behavior while taking medications, such as forgetting doses, skipping treatment, discontinuing therapy when feeling better or worse, and stopping due to side effects. Responses were scored on a 5-point scale (never = 0, rarely = 1, sometimes = 2, often = 3, always = 4), yielding a total score out of 32. Lower scores indicated better adherence. Patients scoring 0 were classified as highly adherent, scores of 1–16 as moderately adherent, 17–24 as low adherent, and 25–32 as non-adherent.

The pharmacist used questionnaire results to identify individual barriers to adherence and provided tailored counseling and education for patients in the intervention group.

Statistical analysis

All findings and data were entered into the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS), version 21 (Chicago, Illinois). Improvements in adherence scores and the number of adherent patients were evaluated as primary outcomes. Normality of data distribution was assessed using the Kolmogorov–Smirnov test prior to analysis.

Associations between patient-related factors and adherence scores were examined as secondary outcomes using multiple regression analysis. Paired sample t-tests were applied to compare baseline and follow-up scores within the same group, while independent sample t-tests were used to compare outcomes between the intervention and control groups. Categorical data were expressed as proportions, and continuous data as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). Statistical significance was set at a threshold of 5% ($\alpha = 0.05$).

Results

General patient characteristics

A total of 80 patients were initially recruited for the study. Six declined participation due to personal reasons or time constraints. Of the 74 patients who signed informed consent, one withdrew for private reasons, leaving 73 patients who completed the study.

Demographic and clinical characteristics

All participants were female. Approximately half were married, with a mean age of 41.81 years (SD = 16.27). The majority were non-smokers (80.8%), and 63.0% had normal weight. The mean number of diseases per patient was 2.21 (SD = 0.98), and the mean number of medications per patient was 2.10 (SD = 1.26). Statistical analysis revealed no significant differences between the intervention and control groups at baseline in demographic or clinical characteristics ($P > 0.05$) (Table 1).

Treatment-Related Problems (TRPs)

The pharmacist identified a total of 177 TRPs across the study sample. The most common TRPs were safety-related issues (31.63%), followed by inappropriate adherence (28.24%) (Fig. 1). Inappropriate knowledge of medications accounted for 8.47% of TRPs. The mean number of TRPs per patient at baseline was 2.42 (SD = 1.06).

Figure 1. Proportion of Treatment-related problems identified for study patients (n = 73)

Counseling and education were the primary interventions used by the pharmacist, representing 46.89% of all interventions. These were particularly effective in addressing adherence-related TRPs. Other interventions included changes in drug therapy, addition of new medications, dose adjustments (increase, decrease, or discontinuation), monitoring, and physician consultation.

Medication adherence scores

There was no significant difference in the adherence score between intervention and control at baseline (P -value = 0.93). About 58% and 51% of patients in the intervention and control groups were reported as adherent to their medications at the beginning of the study. This percentage was increased significantly at follow-up 89% in the active group ($P < 0.001$), while remaining the same for the control group (51.4%, $p = 0.549$; Fig. 2).

The difference in the mean of the adherence score for the intervention group between baseline and follow-up was 2.7, which was statistically significant ($p = 0.003$); in contrast to the control group, this difference was only 0.05 with no significant difference showing ($P = 0.902$) at follow up.

According to the adherence classification categories, none of the patients were classified in the 4th category (non-adherent). At baseline, 28.76% of patients in the intervention group and 26.02% in the control group were classified as high adherent. At follow-up, this percentage was significantly increased to 43.83% in the intervention group ($p = 0.002$); while there was no change in the percentage in the control group (Tables 2–4).

Figure 2. Proportion of adherence in patients at baseline and follow up, P values calculated by pearson chi square test between two groups at intervention and control (control = 37 patient, intervention = 36).

Patients in the study samples had different levels of depression and anxiety. Table 5 represents the number of patients in the total study sample who had mild, moderate or severe level of depression and anxiety.

Association between patient's factors and adherence

Multiple linear regression analysis revealed that there is a significant association between total adherence score and the number of TRPs at follow up. No significant association between adherence score and other patient factor including age, number of diseases per patient, and number of medications per patient was found (Table 6). The most common intervention applied in the study was counseling and educating the patients by the clinical pharmacist, which represented 46.89% of the total number of interventions delivered by the clinical pharmacist. The rest were recommendations sent to the physician regarding changes in the treatment.

Table 1. Demographic and clinical characteristics of the study sample at baseline.

Parameter	Total study sample	Intervention	Control
Total number of patients n(%)	73 (100)	36(49.30)	37(50.70)
Age (year) mean (SD*)	41.81(16.27)	43.28(16.38)	40.38(16.25)
Number of diseases per patient mean (SD)	2.21(0.98)	2.33(1.17)	2.08(0.75)
Number of medications per patient mean (SD)	2.10(1.26)	2.36(1.41)	1.84(1.04)
Weight (Kg) mean, (SD)	64.76(9.50)	64.63(9.39)	64.89(9.74)
BMI Mean, (SD)	24.84(3.68)	24.68(3.52)	24.99(3.88)
Body mass index category, n%			
Underweight	3(4.10)	1(2.80)	2(5.40)
Normal	46(63.01)	25(69.44)	21(56.75)
Overweight	14(19.17)	6(16.66)	8(21.60)
Obese	10(13.69)	4(11.11)	6(16.21)
Marital status, n(%)			
Married	36(49.31)	19(52.77)	17(45.94)
Single	31(42.46)	15(41.66)	16(43.24)
Widow	5(6.84)	1(2.77)	4(10.81)
Divorced	1(1.36)	1(2.77)	0(0)
Insurance, n(%)			
Yes	73(100.00)	36(100.00)	37(100.00)
Diet, n(%)			
Regular	70(95.89)	33(91.66)	37(100)
Healthy	3(4.10)	3(8.33)	0(0)
Exercise, n(%)			
No exercise	66(90.41)	32(88.88)	34(91.89)
Regular exercise	7(9.58)	4(11.11)	3(8.10)
Smoking, n(%)			
None	59(80.82)	29(80.55)	30(81.08)
Moderate	12(16.43)	6(16.66)	6(16.21)
Excessive	2(2.73)	1(2.77)	1(2.70)
Caffeine, n(%)			
Low	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)
Moderate	68(93.15)	35(97.22)	33(89.18)
High	5(6.84)	1(2.77)	4(10.81)

n = number

SD = Standard deviation

*P value calculated by Chi square test **P value calculated by Independent sample t-test

Table 2. Comparison of the total adherence scores at baseline and at 3-months follow up of the study.

	Group	mean of adherence score	Std. Deviation	P-value
Adherence score at baseline	Control	3.65	4.973	0.93
	Intervention	3.56	4.960	
Adherence Score at 3- months follow up	Control	3.59	4.723	0.003
	Intervention	.86	2.653	

P values was calculated by independent sample t-test, between two groups at baseline and follow up.

Table 3. Comparison of the total adherence score in the same group at baseline and follow up.

Group	Adherence score at baseline, mean (SD)	Adherence score at follow up, mean (SD)	P-value
Intervention	3.56(4.96)	0.86(2.65)	0.003
Control	3.65(4.97)	3.59(4.72)	0.902

SD = Standard deviation;

P value calculated by *Paired sample t-test.

Table 4. Proportion of participants (n = 73) with adherence score categories.

		High adherence n %	Low adherence n %	Medium adherence n %
Groups at baseline	Control	19(26.02)	1(1.36)	17(23.28)
	Intervention	21(28.76)	0(0.00)	15(20.54)
Groups at follow up	Control	19(26.02)	1(1.36)	17(23.28)
	Intervention	32(43.83)	0 (0.00)	4(5.47)

*None of the patients were categorised in the fourth adherence category 'Nonadherence'.

**In intervention group, significantly increase in percentage of high adherence scores at follow up found.

The results of multiple linear regression resulted in a standardized regression coefficient (R2) of 0.098 and 0.180 respectively, and results showed a significant association for adherence scores and number of TRPs per patient at follow up.

Discussion

This study provides the first evidence from Jordan that pharmacist-led MMR can improve adherence among female patients with psychiatric disorders such as depression and anxiety. Adherence in the intervention group increased significantly at follow-up, while the control group remained unchanged. A significant difference was shown in the mean adherence scores at follow-up for the intervention group versus the control group. These findings highlight the critical role of pharmacists in addressing barriers to adherence in mental health care, where discontinuation of therapy often leads to relapse, hospitalization, and poor outcomes.

The exclusive focus on female patients adds cultural relevance. Women are disproportionately affected by depression and anxiety, and in Jordan, cultural norms may limit their ability to communicate openly with male healthcare

Table 5. Levels of depression and anxiety in patients (total study sample n = 73).

Scale of depression	Normal	Mild	Moderate	Severe
Number of patients	1 patient	4 patients	40 patients	28 patients
Scale of anxiety	Normal	Mild	Moderate	Severe
Number of patients	1 patient	12 patients	36 patients	24 patients

Table 6. Summary of the regression model for medication adherence score (dependent variable) at baseline (A) and follow up (B) and its association with patients characteristic for the study participants (n = 73).

Independent variable	Beta	t	P value
A			
Age	-0.205	-1.745	0.086
Number of disease per patient	-0.266	-1.735	0.087
Number of drugs per patient	0.078	0.504	0.616
Number of TRPs at baseline	0.094	0.815	0.418
B			
Age	-0.061	-0.537	0.593
Number of disease per Patient	0.072	0.486	0.629
Number of drugs per patient	-0.122	-0.807	0.422
Number of TRPs at follow up per patient	0.273	2.046	0.045
Group type (intervention vs. control)	-0.171	-1.262	0.211

TRP, treatment-related problems.

This table shows the output from a multivariable regression analysis in which adherence score (continuous variable out of 32) was the dependent variable at baseline (A) and at follow-up (B). 'Beta' is the standardized regression coefficient. The overall fit of the models was R2 = 0.098, P = 0.129; R2 = 0.180, P = 0.018 respectively.

Bold p values indicate a significant difference.

providers. The involvement of a female pharmacist likely reduced these barriers, fostering trust and enabling more effective counseling. The mean age of participants was 41.81, with an average of 2.10 medications and 2.42 TRPs per patient. These figures are lower than those reported in Jordanian studies of patients with multiple chronic diseases, where medication loads and TRPs were substantially higher (Basheti et al. 2016a, 2016b). This difference underscores the importance of tailoring adherence interventions to specific patient populations.

Our findings are consistent with international studies showing pharmacist interventions improve adherence. For example, adherence increased from 73% to 90% in a Dutch study (Brook et al. 2005), from 48% to 67% in a U.S. study (Finley et al. 2003), and continuation rates beyond three months were 76% versus 51% in a California study (P < 0.001) (Rickles et al. 2006). In Saudi Arabia, adherence scores improved significantly after three and six months, with gains of up to 18% in the intervention group (P < 0.001) (Aljumah and Hassali 2015). Variations across studies likely reflect differences in patient age, comorbidity burden, and measurement methods. In our study, adherence was associated with the number of TRPs

Figure 3. CONSORT diagram showing patient recruitment and retention during the study period.

but not with age, number of diseases, or number of medications, suggesting that in psychiatric care, treatment-related problems and patient perceptions may be more decisive than disease burden.

Non-adherence in psychiatric disorders has serious consequences, including relapse, substance misuse, suicidal ideation, and diminished quality of life (Lindström and Bingefors 2000; Colom and Vieta 2002; Lacro et al. 2002; Al-Qasem et al. 2011; Farooq and Naeem 2014). By improving adherence, pharmacist-led interventions can mitigate these risks and contribute to better long-term outcomes. Pharmaceutical care services have also been shown to improve quality of life by reducing depressive symptoms and reinforcing adherence behaviors (Gomes et al. 2015; Zahida and Binakaj 2016).

Community pharmacy-based studies in other countries have shown similar benefits of pharmacist interventions for patients with depression and anxiety, reinforcing the relevance of our findings. A recent scoping review highlighted that pharmacists in community settings improved adherence through structured counseling, monitoring, and follow-up, particularly among mental health patients who often struggle with continuity of care. Pharmacists are among the most approachable healthcare providers and are well-positioned to support patients with depression in achieving positive treatment outcomes, especially when integrated into primary care and commu-

nity pharmacy models. These international experiences suggest that the improvements observed in our hospital psychiatric clinic-based study could be replicated in Jordanian community pharmacies, expanding access to adherence support beyond specialized psychiatric clinics.

An important contextual factor in this study is that all participants had health insurance, which could facilitate the future integration of pharmacist-led MMR services into routine psychiatric care. Insurance coverage means that such services could be sustainably reimbursed and repeated at appropriate intervals, depending on patient needs. International guidance suggests that medication reviews should be conducted every three to six months for patients with multiple medications, or annually for those with stable regimens (Vergouwen et al. 2003). In our study, the three-month follow-up demonstrated significant improvements in adherence, but repeating MMR sessions at longer intervals could help maintain these gains and address new treatment-related problems as they arise. Similar approaches have been adopted in long-term care settings in Europe and the U.S., where regular pharmacist-led reviews have been shown to reduce adverse drug events and improve adherence (Brook et al. 2005; Grimes et al. 2013; Holvast et al. 2019). Embedding such services into Jordan's healthcare system, supported by insurance coverage, would not only enhance adherence among psychiatric patients but also strengthen continuity of care and reduce the long-term burden of mental illness.

Finally, adherence measurement methods vary across studies and can influence reported outcomes. In our study, the adherence self-report questionnaire was used as a base for the developed, validated and previously used questionnaire in the Jordanian population, which is efficient and low-cost but may overestimate adherence due to social desirability bias (Abed et al. 2026). Other methods, such as electronic monitoring, pharmacy refill data, or therapeutic drug monitoring, have been employed elsewhere (Brook et al. 2005; Grimes et al. 2013; Holvast et al. 2019). While self-report remains practical for routine practice in Jordan, future studies should complement it with objective measures, extend follow-up periods, and include multiple sites to enhance generalizability.

Limitations

This study has several limitations that should be acknowledged. First, the follow-up period was limited to three months, which may not have been sufficient to fully evaluate the long-term efficacy of the intervention in a randomized controlled trial design. Second, the use of a single female pharmacist to both deliver the intervention and assess outcomes may have introduced performance and detection bias. Future studies should consider involving multiple clinical pharmacists and employing independent assessors to strengthen validity.

Third, the MMAS-8 questionnaire, originally developed for hypertension, was used to measure adherence in patients with depression. Additionally, reliance on self-reported questionnaires could have led to overestimation of adherence due to social desirability bias, as some patients may have feared disappointing the healthcare provider conducting the intervention.

Finally, data collection was restricted to a single clinical site, which may limit the generalizability of the findings to broader populations. Future research should expand to multiple sites and longer follow-up periods to provide more robust evidence on the effectiveness of pharmacist-led interventions in improving adherence among patients with depression and anxiety.

Conclusion

This study sheds light on the important role of pharmacists in improving patients' medication adherence through the provision of the MMR services. The intervention resulted in a significant increase in adherence scores and the proportion of adherent patients, with a clear association between the number of TRPs at follow-up and adherence scores. Importantly, all participants had health insurance, which could facilitate the future integration of pharmacist-led MMR services into routine psychiatric care. With insurance coverage, these services could be sustainably reimbursed and repeated every three to six months for patients with complex regimens, or annually for those with stable therapy, depending on individual needs.

Recommendations

While the findings are promising, conclusions should be tempered by the study's limitations. The short follow-up period of three months may not fully capture long-term adherence patterns, and reliance on self-reported adherence measures introduces potential bias, as patients may overestimate their adherence. Larger studies with extended follow-up periods and the use of objective measures such as pharmacy refill data, electronic monitoring, or therapeutic drug levels would strengthen the evidence base.

Future research should also explore the impact of pharmacist-led MMR on clinical outcomes beyond adherence, including depressive symptom improvement, relapse prevention, quality of life, and healthcare costs. Community pharmacy-based studies in other countries have shown that pharmacists can effectively support patients with depression and anxiety through structured counseling and follow-up, improving adherence rates in both Europe and the U.S. Embedding similar services into Jordan's healthcare system, including the different genders and age groups, supported by insurance coverage, would expand access to adherence support beyond hospital clinics, reduce relapse rates, and strengthen continuity of care for psychiatric patients.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

Informed consent from the humans, donors or donors' representatives: University of Jordan Hospital.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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